

ACTION-CENTERED LEADERSHIP PRACTICES OF SCHOOL HEADS IN IMPROVING THE PERFORMANCE AND QUALITY INSTRUCTION OF TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

The researcher focused on determining if action-centered leadership practices of school heads would bring out the improvement to the level of performance and quality instruction of teachers. This study aimed to determine the relationship of action-centered leadership practices of school heads in improving the performance and quality of instruction of teachers. The study utilized descriptive and correlational research designs and the respondents of this study were 128 elementary teachers who are currently teaching in eight (8) schools of Candelaria East District, Division of Quezon S.Y. 2020 - 2021. The researcher used a survey questionnaire through google form as the research instrument in gathering the response of teacher-respondents. As to teacher-respondents' perception in action-centered leadership practices as to task achievement, group management, and individual management, they assessed the given set of indicators as agree or mostly achieved/managed. As to teacher-respondents perception of their teaching performance and quality of instruction, they assessed the given set indicators as agree or very satisfactory and these results revealed that there is a positive significant relationship between action-centered leadership practices on task achievement, group management, and individual management to the level of performance of teachers and quality of instruction. School heads must clearly state the vision of any endeavor he or she wishes to achieve as it greatly affects the teachers and teachers need to always bear in mind the ingredients to have a better teaching performance that would result in quality instruction for their pupils.

Keywords: Action-Centered Leadership, Teachers' Performance, Quality Instruction